

LEARNING SCIENCES AND FORMING THE SCIENTIFIC WORLD VIEW WHEN WORKING WITH YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: In a situation where our society is improving in working with young people, the issue of patriotism education of society members, first of all, the younger generation, is considered a necessity of the time.

Key words: Homeland, development, Teenager, Republic of Uzbekistan, World, Japan, Anubis Korea, Singapore, Malaysia, Law, pedagogical and psychological, Work with young people before the draft.

The indicators of development and progress of the life of our country contain the most realistic information to increase the effectiveness of the process of patriotic education. For example, in Uzbekistan, the percentage of 14-year-old boys whose height indicators of adolescents correspond to the standards of the World Health Organization is 94.2% in our country today, that is, 14-year-old boys the height of our girls grew by 2.8 centimeters on average in the next ten years.

From the day the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, identifying talented young people, organizing an educational process for them in accordance with the requirements of the time, and ensuring their perfection through a differentiated approach to potential young people is considered the main urgent problem. Therefore, the problem of identifying talented young people is a problem that is waiting for its solution. Japan, South Korea, Singapore, and Malaysia, which are among the developed countries of the world, despite the fact that their land area is not large and their natural resources are limited, one of the main reasons why they

occupy high economic positions is their rational and appropriate use of intellectual resources.

In the above-mentioned countries, attention is focused on identifying talented young people while organizing the educational process on the basis of the latest achievements of science and technology, creating a foundation for students' solid acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities. One of the principles envisaged in the National Personnel Training Program implemented in our country is aimed at identifying talented young people and effectively organizing the educational process, taking into account their interests and needs. The issue of selecting talented young people and paying special attention to them has always been on the agenda of our country.

The following are the main regulatory and legal documents in force on working with young people before the draft:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defense", May 11, 2001.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On general military obligation and military service", December 12, 2002.
3. The Regulation "On the organization of initial training before the draft and the procedure for its implementation", approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 348 of December 18, 2014.
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports", September 4, 2015.
5. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Regulation on the selection procedure and admission rules for higher military educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan", June 3, 2014.
6. Charter of "Vatanparvar" organization, which supports the Defense of Uzbekistan. It was registered in the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 4, 2016.

Changes in the field of organizing work with young people before the draft and preparing young people for the defense of the Motherland require improvement of

the content, as well as organizational and methodological aspects of military-patriotic education to the level of current requirements.

For this purpose, it is necessary to choose and implement effective forms and methods of education and training for working with young people before the draft, to search for new forms and methods that can fully fulfill the tasks of military-patriotic education in the current conditions and to implement them, to implement educational activities. efficiency should be analyzed.

In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the effectiveness of the forms and methods of military patriotism education from the organizational, pedagogical and psychological aspects and their orientation to the development of the personality of the defender of the Motherland.

Formation of a scientific worldview in the future defenders of the Motherland by teaching the basics of a number of modern sciences is considered a necessary condition for the implementation of military-patriotic education in modern times.

It is necessary to take into account that each subject has its own importance for the formation and strengthening of patriotic qualities. In this case, each of the social sciences, exact sciences, natural sciences, languages, applied sciences is important in acquiring the relevant military specialty.

At the same time, the contributions and discoveries made by many of our great ancestors, world-famous scientists and thinkers who lived on the soil of our Motherland during the stages of the origin and historical development of these sciences, and the fact that they are now considered universal human values. Acquaintance with information is necessary to expand the scope of knowledge of future military personnel, to increase their outlook and cultural level.

It can be concluded from the above that it is necessary to improve the work in this direction at a modern level, taking into account the fact that further improvement of military-patriotic education of young people is of urgent importance. This requires the following:

improving the regulatory and legal bases on the issues of military-patriotic education at a modern level;

organization of a system of patriotic education based on social partnership activities with organizations interested in military-patriotic education;

defining and implementing specific goals and tasks of the participants of this system in terms of patriotic education;

improving the scientifically based content and methods of the military-patriotic education system;

improving the educational and material basis and scientific-methodical support in the areas of military-patriotic education at a modern level, etc.

The issue of regularly developing and activating military-patriotic education of young people, taking into account the existing experiences in this direction and the positive results achieved, is the demand of the times.

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